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JEM-Joining Educational Mathematics

Implementation of Authors' Support

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Author(s)	<i>Christine Müller</i>

eContentplus

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exploitable.

¹ OJ L 79, 24.3.2005, p. 1.

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Work package 6 is responsible for organizing promotion activities and disseminating sample material which shows the benefits of using semantic mark-up in e-learning in mathematics. This includes also education about proper usage of eLearning metadata standards. In JEM, the dissemination of user experience, guidelines, HOWTO's has been organized by setting up an authors' wiki on the network portal and preparing the framework for the implementation of a hotline, when requested. The portal already supports discussion forums moderated by JEM members, the creation of FAQs, and a collection of success stories in terms of Case Studies.

This document provides details at the authors' wiki itself as well as points out some of the progress in the dissemination of user experience, authors' guidelines, and HOWTO's.

The authors' and users' wiki

The JEM authors' and users' wiki² is located in the JEM portal. These collaborative pages coordinate knowledge dissemination and discussion of topics that are relevant to authors of eContent in mathematics but also to end-users or eContent who are just interested in using materials produced by a third party (e.g. IPR issues). Registration to these pages is open to all those who are interested in exchanging mathematical digital content, in discussing optimal ways to produce electronic notes with mathematical formulae, or to introduce interactive mathematical exercises and other learning materials in their teaching.

This section describes the basic design of the authors' support pages and their purpose. Please refer to Deliverable 6.1 (Mueller, 2007) for further details of the goals and guidelines of the authors' wiki.

Overview

The authors' Wiki on the JEM portal can be accessed by anyone, unregistered or registered, through the "Wiki" link in the "Community" menu in the left hand-side column.

JEM - Joining Educational Mathematics
eContentPlus Thematic Network

JEM

- ※ Home
- ※ Network Rules
- ※ About us
- ※ Publications
- ※ Related Projects
- ※ FAQs
- ※ News

COMMUNITY

- ※ Forums
- ※ Polls
- ※ Wiki
- ※ Recent posts
- ※ Blogs
- ※ Members

The goal of the JEM thematic network is to pool together the requirements for the coordination of content enrichment activities in the area of mathematics, agreed standards and to the delivery of powerful synoptic high-quality pages, invoked in e-learning platforms operated by the partners.

NEW AND EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES IN MATH EDUCATION

Submitted by mikaseppa

Timezone: Etc/GMT+3

Porthania Building, Lecture Hall IV
Yliopistonkatu 3
University of Helsinki
August 17-18, 2007

Wiki can be found here

The Wiki on the JEM portal includes various sections for different purposes and among them there is the one geared to Authors' and the one geared to Users'. This distinction differentiates topics which can be of more technical nature from pedagogical, methodological and legal aspects of introducing ICT in mathematics teaching.

² <http://www.jem-thematic.net/wiki>

- COMMUNITY
- ⌘ Forums
- ⌘ Polls
- ⌘ Wiki
 - ⌘ Authors' wiki
 - ⌘ Developers' wiki
 - ⌘ Users' wiki
- ⌘ Recent posts
- ⌘ Blogs
- ⌘ Members

The author's wiki is now fully integrated into the JEM portal and does not require a separate account, as it did in the former release.

The wiki aims to collect the existing expertise of the members of the network and the latest innovation in areas influencing authoring eContent and optimizing the creation of high-quality instructional materials.

Structure

There are several sections devoted to different aspects of authoring educational content in the authors' wiki. At the moment these include:

Accessibility Aspects: Approaches and Methods to improve the accessibility of mathematical documents, e.g. by using semantic mark-up formats, like OpenMath and MathML, to represent the mathematical fragments in the digital resources and, which in particular facilitates the automatic generation of accessible mathematical content.

Authoring Tools and Software: This section reviews software and tools for authoring course material in mathematics. Here contributors to the wiki can enter their description of authoring software using the Software template as a guideline. Software descriptions are added to the wiki by the editor. The template has been designed so that readers can get a quick, synoptic overview of existing tools and find pointers to contact the developers or the user support, to read discussions, to check and report bugs.

e-Authors in JEM: The JEM network collects together leading European universities and companies which have high-quality special knowledge and experience in digital content in mathematics. A quick inventory of the digital content within the network shows that all partners qualify as stakeholders for eContent in mathematics, statistics, and theoretical physics. This section illustrates the quality and volume of the content owned by some of the partners of this proposal. Eventually it will expand to a full repository of JEM sample content that demonstrates best practice.

Intellectual Property Rights: This section deals with IPR issues for content developed within universities or paid by public funding vary from country to country. In some countries the professors authoring digital content also own the IPR of that content while in other the IPR belongs to the university at which the authors are working. Contributions are expected from each partner on their respective policies.

Issues in Quality of eLearning: This section is a survey/study on quality certification for eLearning content in mathematics. JEM will base its review process and guidelines on the results of this study. As a side effect, this will provide quality competence for JEM authors who will become familiar with the quality criteria used to assess the resources they produce. Quality in eLearning resources and programs is a rather novel topic and still subject of debate. A survey-based approach will start to collect the practice in partners' institutions.

Multilingual and Multicultural Aspects: Since different types of context may influence the choice of a mathematical notation and language, state-of-the-art technologies need to be employed to derive localized presentations of the mathematical fragments in digital documents from language-independent semantic representations of the content of its subject material. This section points to factors that influence the way mathematics is written and discusses solutions for producing multilingual material.

Contributing to the authors' support handbook

Unregistered guest users are allowed to read all pages of the wiki, including the comments. They however cannot post comments or add new pages. Only registered users, after approval by the JEM network administration, are able to write articles to the wiki. The comments are reviewed by editors before publishing. Editing a new page for the wiki is rather straightforward. It can be done by filling an online form where basic formatting of the article can be made with special commands. Textual descriptions can be entered as HTML or using wiki-like syntax, depending on the user's preference. Guidelines to editing the wiki are given at <http://jem-thematic.net/howto>, they are constantly updated as new functionalities are added to the portal.

The screenshot shows the JEM - Joining Educational Mathematics website interface. The header includes the logo and navigation links like 'My account', 'Search', and 'Feedback'. The main content area displays the 'MULTILINGUAL AND MULTICULTURAL ASPECTS' page with a form for editing. The form includes fields for 'Title', 'Parent', 'Content', 'Topic', and 'Body'. The 'Content' field has a dropdown menu set to '<none>' and a note: 'Taxonomy used to collect logically the types of book pages - must be used only on cover pages'. The 'Body' field contains the text: 'Since different types of context may influence the choice of a mathematical notation and language, state-of-the-art technologies need to be employed to derive localized presentations of the mathematical'. On the right side, there is a 'UPCOMING EVENTS' section listing several events with their respective dates and item counts.

For some topics, such as “Software” and “Case study”, users should select the corresponding Content Type from the list shown in their personal menu when choosing “Create content”. These templates were specifically created to ensure that a certain level of detail and uniformity is provided across the entire portal. Moreover, information collected via these templates can be reused and displayed in various sections of the portal and allows for sustainable maintenance.

Concerning users’ and authors’ support, the Software templates prompts developers to enter information about the user Manual, the user mailing list and the contact person for user support. Additionally, a community scoring scheme is set up for evaluation of the software that can collect feedback in form of reviews from authors’ and users’.

[Home](#)

USE OF THE STACK COMPUTER AIDED ASSESSMENT SYSTEM WITH FIRST YEAR UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS.

[View](#) [Edit](#) [Outline](#) [Track](#)

Submitted by Chris Sengwin on Wed, 08/22/2007 - 18:24 [Assessment](#) [undergraduate mathematics](#)

In the academic year 2006-2007 we have been using the STACK computer aided assessment system with undergraduate mathematics students. This has taken place both at the University of Birmingham and the University of Warwick, UK.

Challenges:
The pilot at the University of Warwick was especially useful to us as the development team in Birmingham as it involved a totally independent team who downloaded, installed and used the system for an academic year. Staff development took place to enable colleagues to learn the highly technical aspects of authoring their own learning materials in the STACK format. We received detailed feedback from (i) their students and (ii) the colleagues authoring their own questions. Both have guided the further development of the system from Jan 2007 onwards. The reports we received from them took the form of a detailed written report and site visits for interviews with key staff.

Successes:
Colleagues were able to install and use STACK with their students. After staff development sessions they were able to author questions, with support being provided for technical questions on the obscure syntax of the Maxima computer algebra system. Students very much liked the obvious (to them) mathematical sophistication of the STACK system and the course questionnaires were positive. Many students considered STACK to be a useful tool to help them learn mathematics and practice important mathematical techniques.

Lessons learned:
We received detailed feedback about the interactions students had with STACK. These can be grouped into two categories. (1) The overall design on the interactions and web-page navigation needed to use STACK. These observations have been very useful in guiding the current round of software development. (2) Key to any mathematical software is the input of mathematical expressions by students. This is a very difficult issue to resolve since traditional mathematical

[Home](#) » [Create content](#)

SUBMIT CASE STUDY

Describe the general setup of the case study

Title: *
panta rhei - an interactive collaborative community reader

Case study classification:
collaborative assessment and learning
Use keywords to index the case study

Description:
The case study of panta rhei will take place with the General Computer Science lecture (GenCS) at the Jacobs University. Here, panta rhei promotes the discussion of lecture material between students and TAs and, in particular, supports students’ activities, e.g. the browsing of course material, the posting of questions referencing the course material or other postings as well as the search for postings and course material. In addition, panta rhei supports the assessment of forum postings (helpful, correct, trustworthy) and course pages (relevance, soundness, and presentation).

D 6.2 Implementation of the Developers' Support

Home » Wiki » Users' wiki » Case Studies

CASE STUDIES IN DIAGNOSTIC ASSESSMENT

View Edit Track

One of the primary use for assessment system is for the diagnostic testing of students knowledge prior entering a new school or curriculum. This section is devoted to collecting case studies for diagnosis of mathematical background. Case studies should point out the assessment system used, the design of the assessment tests and the methodologies employed in the diagnostic testing. Efficiency of the test, drawbacks, possible improvements are all aspects that can be discussed in each study.

- Use of the STACK computer aided assessment system with first year undergraduate students.

Case Studies up Use of the STACK computer aided assessment system with first year undergraduate students. >

Go to previous page

Add child page Printer-friendly version Add new comment 85 reads mark as spam mark as not spam report as spam Subscribe post

The pedagogical and methodological insights of JEM members can be collected by supplying “Case study” descriptions consisting of a title, a classification in terms of free keywords (a folksonomy), and short paragraphs on Challenges, Successes, Lesson learned. Additional publications related to the case study can be linked as references. Wiki editors have the option to link both the Software and

the Case study items as pages in the wiki.

Finally, note also that the contributor to any item on the JEM portal may subscribe to reactions and receives notifications when comments are posted as reply to the published item.

To contact the editorial board of the wiki, any users of the JEM portal may utilize the “Contact” button on the header menu. It is good practice to do so when one adds new Software or a new Case study so that it may be linked to the JEM wiki.

Implementation of the authors' handbook

Please refer to Deliverable D5.2 (Pauna 2007) for technical implementation details of the wiki.

Contributions by the JEM Partners

Many contributions have been made, especially during the JEM workshops and seminars, which allowed all members to spread their successes as well as lessons learned, to establish new connections, and to gather feedback and innovated ideas how to carry on their work. Some of these contributions are given here as sample content to be found online. The complete overview can be found by consulting the full list on the JEM publication pages³.

Recent contributions from the JEM Seminar on “New and Emerging Technologies” organized by UH in Helsinki on August 17-18, include

- an overview presentation on *Use Cases for Assessment in Math Education*, more specifically homework assignments for university course Single Variable Calculus,

³ <http://jem-thematic.net/publications>

- formative tests in high schools, diagnostic tests in Stadia technical engineering school have been discussed. (cf. <http://jem-thematic.net/node/358>)
- ***Experience in deploying novel information Technology in Education*** at Texas A&M was discussed by the director of their Distance Education program. He reported that institutions now recognize that information technology can assist them in their operations and in fulfilling their educational mission, and that e-education solutions have developed greater robustness, ease of use, and functionality. Moreover, “traditional” objections to adoption and acceptance have decreased. (cf. <http://jem-thematic.net/node/355>)
 - ***How to use Diagnosing Entrance Profiles at UPC to improve learning*** is the presentation of the novel diagnosis entrance profiles that been adopted for this year’s freshmen to allow for an early detection of mathematical weaknesses of their students. They are particularly benefiting from the JEM Network by gaining feedback on their system as well as by establishing connections to other schools that will also deploy their entrance profiles. (cf. <http://jem-thematic.net/node/357>)
 - ***Workarounds for mathematical writing and editing*** is a topic which is very often discussed at JEM meetings. The latest presentation raising this issue was by the Norwegian JEM partner on their practical workarounds for the problem of handwritten assignments submitted electronically during the undergraduate mathematics initiative DELTA. (cf. <http://jem-thematic.net/node/353>)

Continuing on the topic of producing high-quality learning material, the JEM meeting held in conjunction with the OpenMath workshop featured a high number of tutorial presentations by leaders in their field.

- ***How to use enhanced pen-based interface for mathematical computing:*** As pen-based computing becomes more prevalent, it is increasingly important to be able to share ink across applications and across platforms. The emerging standard Ink Mark-up Language (InkML) is intended for this purpose. Four drafts of the proposed standard have been produced since 2003, resulting in a specification with broad input from industry and invited experts. The talk by S. Watt, one of the editors of the InkML specification, and director of the Ontario Research Centre for Computer Algebra, presented an overview of InkML and discussed how it may be used to enhance pen-based interfaces for mathematical computing.
- ***How to implement flexible elisions into mathematical documents:*** Mathematicians frequently elide brackets or symbols in formulae to concentrate on essential facts and to avoid distract experienced mathematicians with notation that can easily be deduced from context. The JEM partner JACU proposes an extension of the notation specification infrastructure in OMDoc by functionality for flexible elisions, in

particular, by this they allow authors' to create documents that adapt to the reader's need. (cf. <http://jem-thematic.net/node/164>)

Users' feedback, such as the DELTA experience mentioned above, is also represented by several publications. We only highlight one.

- ***Experiences in using new technologies on an every day basis***: this position presentation discusses the usual problems that an instructor faces when using technology in his or her everyday work. While it emphasized that standards are crucial, it strongly suggests that such is the ease of use as well. As a consequence of the latter, software tools such as PowerPoint emerges as probably the most important tool facilitating the job of an instructor. In synchronous on-line teaching situations, there is almost no choice today. The development of instructional technology is very fast and current technical solutions may become obsolete in several months rather than years. Raising the question 'will PowerPoint still prevail', this presentation provoked they several discussion (cf. <http://jem-thematic.net/node/168>) and presented the users' feedback to the audience of technology developers.

Sample solutions, experience reports and case studies are presented often, both online and during meetings. Developers themselves made an effort to produce tutorial presentations that are not only technically oriented but address a general users' audience.

- ***How to make mathematical teaching material more interactive***: TU/e has developed a web-based mathematics method for Dutch high schools, which is currently being developed jointly with a team of high school teachers in the Netherlands. The project's aim is to produce a new generation of high quality teaching material incorporating various forms of interactivity. (cf. <http://jem-thematic.net/node/308>) In the effort to support users, they have supplied an online MathDox manual, which guides the reader through the installation process of the [MathDox Player](#), The MathDox architecture, and a tutorial about creating MathDox documents. (cf. <http://jem-thematic.net/node/170>)
- ***Experience in teaching mathematics to distance students***: FernUni Hagen, but also UOC, shared their experience and the sample material used during their mathematics courses for computer science and mathematics students both online and during JEM meetings. Courses offered through the web are enriched with various web based e-learning tools such as tools for experiments and visualizations, CAS-supported exercises and drills, CAS-based specialized calculators (for matrix calculations, modular arithmetic, encryption and decryption), and flashcards. (cf. <http://jem-thematic.net/node/339>)
- ***How to make documents more dynamic and adaptable***: JACU has explored the use of documents as interfaces to mathematical knowledge and proposed an

augmented document model that facilitates the selection of appropriate presentations for all symbols in the document. Separating the notation context from the structure and content of a document, allows identifying the author's selection of notation and his notation practices. This further facilitates the identification of communities of practice sharing specific notation preferences and the adaptation of documents to the notation preferences of groups of readers and co-authors. Additional advantages are ease of referencing and context's reuse, both contributing to reduce the author's workload during the authoring process. (cf. <http://jem-thematic.net/node/169>)

Dissemination of national users' groups activities has been reported by the Dutch partners in their progress reports and can be consulted by all registered users. This is an example of how information about specific activities of interests to the JEM community can be published on the portal and may lead to further progress:

- **Platform for exchanging knowledge experiences:** The JEM partners TU/e and UvA, among others, are contributing to the Dutch SIGMA project, which aims to facilitate continuous learning paths in education in mathematics between secondary education and higher education. Working groups have been formed to address national synchronization of entry tests, standards for assessment, SIGMA-award for best practice in transition issues. (cf. <http://jem-thematic.net/node/352>)

Sample new content is also being disseminated to serve as inspiration for other authors or to be taken up and used elsewhere.

- **e-authors in JEM:** UOC has been working on the definition of a taxonomy and an ontology for a repository of mathematical learning objects for the UOC, in collaboration with the UOC Spanish project Personal (personalization of the learning process). They have also been working on a multilingual (Spanish, Catalan and English) repository of verbalized locutions of mathematical formulas and have implemented a web-based course in Complex Numbers and Functions (available in Spanish and in Catalan) with interactive examples, activities and exercises by using the calculator Wiris (on-line), and verbalized formulas in the Catalan version (cf. <http://jem-thematic.net/node/230>)

Conclusions

We discussed how the JEM network has implemented functionalities and utilities raise awareness in new technologies that are key ingredients for creating high-quality content in mathematics. We emphasized the collaborative nature of the JEM portal where the community

should find relevant information concerning guidelines, example and case studies that document the affectivity of ICT in mathematics education.

Bibliography

Mueller, Christine. *Authors' wiki*. Deliverable 6.1, JEM Thematic Network, 2007.